

CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC INVESTIGATION OF ARTOSTENONE, THE STENONE ISOLATED FROM THE INDIAN SUM- MER FRUIT, *ARTOCARPUS INTEGRIFOLIA* BY MEANS OF GONIOMETER AND X-RAYS.

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Several morphological examinations have been made by means of the goniometer. The crystal system has been found to be monoclinic. Plate faces $a(100)$ of the crystals exhibit pronounced elongation along the c -axis. Crystallographic studies by means of X-rays gives $a = 17.3$, $b = 10.2$, $c = 7.4$ and $\beta = 100^\circ 49'$. The molecular weight as calculated from these results comes out to be 424.2 ($C_{30}H_{50}O$ requiring 426 as the molecular weight). The improbability of the presence of the CO group in the position C_3 , as in ergosterol, cholesterol etc., has been supported. The results supply additional support to the view that artostenone has got almost the same molecular structure as that of ergosterol.

The knowledge of the constitution of sterols, bile acids and related compounds has been revolutionised in the year 1932. The new conception first grew out of X-ray investigations by Bernal (*Nature*, 1932, **129**, 277, 721), who for the first time suggested that the then accepted formulae for sterols and bile acids, must be modified in order that they could be made to fit into the crystallographic cell. About three months after the publication of this paper, a new formula was suggested by Rosenheim and King (*Chem. Ind.*, 1932, **51**, 464, 954), which was later modified by Weiland and Dane (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1932, **210**, 268). This has been supported by crystallographic evidence (Bernal, *Chem. Ind.*, 1932, **51**, 466) and accepted universally. Crystal structure of several sex hormones from various sources, has also been determined recently with the help of X-rays (Bernal and Crowfoot, *Z. Krist.*, 1936, **93**, 464) and many valuable informations obtained.

It has been shown in previous papers (Nath, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1937, **247**, 9; 1937, **249**, 71, 76, 78), that artostenone resembles other sterols and stenones very closely, the only differences being in the position of CO group and the double bond.

Crystallographic investigation was undertaken with a view to determine the molecular structure and thus to obtain further evidence, if possible, of the close relationships, secured by chemical methods, between artostenone and the other known sterols and hormones.

Artostenone, when crystallised from a solution of alcohol-benzene-ethyl acetate mixture (3:2:1), forms fine crystals in the form of thick plates. These crystals have been examined both by the goniometer and X-rays. The preliminary results obtained are sufficient to give an idea as to the molecular weight, and shape and size of the complex artostenone molecule.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Goniometer Results.

The plate faces $a(100)$, of the crystals, exhibit pronounced elongation along the c -axis. Several morphological examinations by the goniometer supply the following data.

TABLE I.

Crystal system	...	Monoclinic.
Axial ratios as $a : b : c = 1.686 : 1 : 0.7306$ (1.683 : 1 : 0.7269 from X-ray data).		
Axial angle $\beta = 100^\circ 49'$.		
Observed forms : $a(100)$, $c(001)$, $p(110)$ and $x(101)$.		
Interfacial angles : $a : p = 58^\circ 52'$; $p : p = 62^\circ 18'$; $a : c = 79^\circ 11'$; $a : x = 75^\circ 57'$.		

Fig. 1 represents the structural sketch.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

X-ray Results.

X-ray rotation photographs about the three principal crystal axes (as represented in Figures 2, 3 and 4) have been taken to determine the axial lengths and the size of the unit cell which comes out to be as follows

$$a_0 = 17.25, \quad b_0 = 10.25, \quad c_0 = 7.45 \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = 100^\circ 49'.$$

Density of the crystal has been found to be 1.083 by Retger's suspension method. Assuming the number of chemical molecules per unit cell to be two, the molecular weight comes out to be 424.2, which agrees well with the value (426) as determined by chemical method and required for the formula $C_{30}H_{50}O$, proposed for artostenone, in previous works (*loc. cit.*).

DISCUSSION.

Since there are two molecules in a unit cell, it can be assumed that the longest direction is along the a -axis, thickness along the c -axis and the b -axis is twice the breadth of the molecule.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

According to the models made to scale of the formula (I) of Rosenheim and King for ergosterol and its dimensions measured with due allowance for the space occupied by hydrogens, the results obtained are

Author's results ... $a = 4.5\text{\AA}$; $b = 7.4\text{\AA}$; $c = 20.0\text{\AA}$.

Bernal's results ... $a = 4.9\text{\AA}$; $b = 7.4\text{\AA}$; $c = 19.6\text{\AA}$.

It has been shown in previous papers (*loc. cit.*) that in artostenone there is no OH group in structural formula (I) given below. Hence if the molecule is also assumed to be of the same model as (I), the length should be

shorter by about $1.5\text{\AA}$. The other difference is that there is no double bond in the side-chain; but this should not change the dimensions appreciably.

Thus the molecular dimensions of artostenone as calculated from this cell comes out to be

$$a = 17.3\text{\AA}, \quad b = 7.4, \quad c = 5.1;$$

and those required by model (II) are

$$a = 4.9\text{\AA}, \quad b = 7.4 \quad \text{and} \quad c = 18.1$$

[as obtained after due allowance for the modifications stated above, from Bernal's values for ergosterol (*Nature*, 1932, 129, 277)].

The agreement between the size of the artostenone molecule with that of ergosterol, is very close and that confirms very nicely the similarity between the structure of the carbon skeletons of these two compounds.

The result further settles conclusively another point regarding the structure of the side-chain. In case of ergosterol the chain has been found to be

An additional carbon atom beyond this chain in the linear direction will obviously necessitate a greater length for an artostenone molecule. If the chain in the artostenone molecule is assumed to be

or

or something like this, the length of the molecule should be the same as that of ergosterol, and this has actually been observed in case of artostenone. Thus there are indications to show that artostenone, like ergosterol, also contains four condensed rings and a side-chain with five carbon atoms in the linear direction, other carbon atoms forming branches of the main line in some way or other.

Our best thanks are due to Prof. J. C. Ghosh and Prof. S. N. Bose for their kind and sympathetic interest and to Dr. K. Banerjee for his helpful advice and criticism in this work.

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Received April 6, 1939.